

Photochemical Reduction of Uranyl Ion with Tri-*p*-Tolylphosphine

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Photochemical reduction of uranyl ion with tri-*p*-tolylphosphine is temperature independent and obeys second order kinetics. Higher value of chemical quenching constant k_q , 165.0 LM^{-1} for tri-*p*-tolylphosphine as compared to that for triphenylphosphine 147.0 LM^{-1} suggests participation of inductive effect of methyl group at *p*-position. A dynamic mechanism for oxygen atom transfer from excited uranyl ion to ground state of tri-*p*-tolylphosphine has been suggested.

THE photochemistry of uranyl ion has been studied employing flash photolysis and esr techniques. It has been shown that organic compounds reduce uranyl ion via inter or intra electron transfer or via hydrogen atom abstraction from the carbon atom adjacent to an activating group such as -CO-, -CN-, -COOH-, -CHO-, -OH-, -CONH₂ or -COOR^{1,2}. In earlier investigations on photochemical reduction of uranyl ion with triphenylphosphine, triphenylarsine, triphenylantimony and triphenylbismuth, oxygen atom transfer from uranyl ion to the substrates has been suggested³. In the present investigation, kinetics and mechanism for photochemical reduction of uranyl ion with tri-*p*-tolylphosphine have been investigated.

Methods and Material :

Uranyl acetate (B.D.H., England) and sulphuric acid (B.D.H.) AnalaR grade were used as such and tri-*p*-tolylphosphine was prepared and purified as reported in the literature⁴. Double distilled deionized water-acetone (AnalaR grade) (3:7 v/v) were used as the reaction medium. Photochemical reduction was investigated in pyrex glass photochemical reactor. Temperature of the reaction mixture was controlled by circulating water with MK-70 cryostat. Oxygen free nitrogen gas was flushed through the reaction mixture and its progress was followed by observing the concentration of uranium(IV) formation with VSU 2-P spectrophotometer. Quantum yield for uranium(IV) formation was determined using potassium ferrioxalate as an actinometer⁵.

Results and Discussion

Photochemical reduction of uranyl ion with tri-*p*-tolylphosphine follows pseudo first order kinetics with respect to each of the uranyl ion and tri-*p*-tolylphosphine and overall reaction was of second order. Rate and quantum yield for uranium(IV) formation are linear functions of tri-*p*-tolylphosphine concentration (Table I).

Tertiary phosphines have electronic absorption spectra in the region 250-300 nm (due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$

transition). Pyrex glass photochemical reactor cut off electromagnetic radiations $<365 \text{ nm}$.

TABLE I—QUANTUM YIELD (ϕ) FOR URANIUM(IV) FORMATION AND SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS [K] $I_0 = 3.02 \times 10^{16} \text{ q/s}$ AND $T = 30^\circ$

$[\text{UO}_2^{2+}]_{\text{ML}^{-1}}$	$[\text{t-}p\text{-TP}]_{\text{ML}^{-1}}$	$[\text{H}^+]_{\text{ML}^{-1}}$	ϕ	K min^{-1}
0.005	0.010	0.40	0.22	0.250
0.010	0.010	0.40	0.22	0.161
0.015	0.010	0.40	0.20	0.108
0.020	0.010	0.40	0.23	0.075
0.025	0.010	0.40	0.24	0.090
0.010	0.0050	0.40	0.17	0.260
0.010	0.0075	0.40	0.19	0.184
0.010	0.0100	0.40	0.22	0.161
0.010	0.0150	0.40	0.27	0.132
0.010	0.010	0.10	0.09	0.066
0.010	0.010	0.20	0.15	0.108
0.010	0.010	0.40	0.22	0.161
0.010	0.010	0.80	0.27	0.200

Protonation of uranyl ion with sulphuric acid shows a blue shift of 10 nm. However, addition of tri-*p*-tolylphosphine does not show any change in the spectra, ruling out any ground state interaction between the reactants, indicating that uranyl ion is the only species which absorb the light radiations in the visible region. In the kinetic study of photoaccelerated uranium(IV)-uranium(VI) electron exchange reaction, it has been observed that radiations 540-550 nm and $<600 \text{ nm}$, which are absorbed by uranium(IV) are inefficient for photoacceleration reaction. Hence uranyl ion is the only photoactive species⁶.

During excitation of uranyl ion with lowest energy (singlet $\rightarrow$ triplet) transition, the electron moves from π -bonding highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) consisting of uranium 5f- and 6d-, and oxygen 2p-orbitals to lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) mainly of uranium 5f-orbitals⁷. Consequently, increased electron density on the uranium atom reduces the net charge on it. Excitation of uranyl ion to higher singlet state may intercross to the lowest state which, because of its

sufficient energy and longer life time (spin forbidden nature of Triplet→Singlet), is the more reactive state. Oxidation potential of the uranyl ion in the excited state (2.6V) is higher as compared to that in the ground state (0.05V)⁹. Excitation of uranyl ion imparts to it some free radical character as a result of which U=O bond length is increased⁷.

Product analysis of the photolysed solution shows a strong absorption band at 660 nm corresponding to uranium(IV) formation. Infrared absorption band at 1120 cm⁻¹ of photolysed product (green crystals) shows co-ordinated phosphoryl group, whereas the infrared absorption band at 1190 cm⁻¹ is due to tri-*p*-tolylphosphine oxide extracted with benzene from decomposed products in concentrated hydrochloric acid.

In the tri-*p*-tolylphosphine, phosphorus atom has low-lying vacant d-orbitals for π-bonding with oxygen 2p-orbitals⁹. The π-bonding ability of phosphorus atom facilitates transfer of oxygen atom from excited uranyl ion to tri-*p*-tolylphosphine. The inductive effect of methyl group at *para* position further increases the strength of σ-bond in addition to π-bonding of the phosphoryl group.

The temperature independent nature of the photochemical reduction of uranyl ion with tri-*p*-tolylphosphine eliminates collisional electronic energy transfer^{1,10}. First excited state of tri-*p*-tolylphosphine is above the luminescent state (lowest triplet) of uranyl ion. Deactivation via collisional energy transfer from excited uranyl ion to ground state of tri-*p*-tolylphosphine is an endothermic process, not favoured energetically.

The photochemical reduction of uranyl ion may proceed by electron transfer via transient species, uranium(V), which in aqueous acidic solution immediately disproportionates to uranium(IV) and uranium(VI). Absence of electronic absorption band at 636 nm and 750 nm due to uranium(V) does not favour the electron transfer mechanism for photochemical reduction of uranyl ion with tri-*p*-tolylphosphine¹¹.

In view of above, a dynamic mechanism of oxygen atom transfer through exciplex formation has been suggested for photochemical reduction of uranyl ion with tri-*p*-tolylphosphine. Donor-acceptor interaction arises between the two in the excited state, although there is no affinity in the ground state.

The mechanism of the reactions is represented in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

where *t-p-TP* is tri-*p*-tolylphosphine, k_1 is the fluorescence deactivation rate constant, k_2 , k_3 and k_6 are radiationless deactivation rate constants, k_4 is the chemical quenching rate constant, which determine the rate of chemical quenching of excited uranyl ion by ground state of tri-*p*-tolylphosphine and k_5 is the chemical decomposition deactivation of exciplex rate constant. Employing steady state principle for intermediates, a mathematical relation between the rate constants and quantum yield for uranium(IV) formation is derived :

$$\frac{1}{\phi} = \left[1 + \frac{k_6}{k_5}\right] \left[1 + \frac{k_1 + k_2 + k_3[\text{UO}_2^{2+}]}{k_4[t\text{-}p\text{-TP}]}\right] \quad \dots (8)$$

Plot between ϕ^{-1} versus reciprocal of tri-*p*-tolylphosphine concentration is a straight line (Fig. 1) with an intercept $1 + \frac{k_6}{k_5} = 2.75$. Low values of quantum yield (ϕ) and $\frac{k_6}{k_5} = 1.75$ ($k_6 > k_5$) show that contribution of radiationless deactivation of excited uranyl ion is more as compared to the contribution made by chemical deactivation.

Fig. 1

Ratio of the intercept to slope gives the magnitude of chemical quenching constant k_q , which is a measure of radiationless chemical quenching of the opti-

cally excited uranyl ion.

$$\frac{\text{Intercept}}{\text{Slope}} = \frac{k_4}{k_1 + k_2 + k_3[\text{UO}_2^{2+}]} = kq \quad \dots (9)$$

$$\text{or } kq = \tau_0 k_4$$

$$\text{where } \tau_0 = \frac{1}{k_1 + k_2 + k_3[\text{UO}_2^{2+}]}$$

Higher value of $kq = 165.0 \text{ LM}^{-1}$ for tri-*p*-tolylphosphine as compared to that for triphenylphosphine⁸ 147.0 LM^{-1} is due to the inductive effect of methyl group present at the *para* position in phenyl group in triphenylphosphine.

Stern-volmer plot of $\frac{I_0}{I_f} = 1 + k_{sv} [Q]$ (Fig. 2.)

where I_0 and I_f are the fluorescence intensities in the absence and in the presence of quencher tri-*p*-tolylphosphine is a straight line with an intercept=1 and $K_{sv} = 222.2 \text{ LM}^{-1}$. Greater values of $K_{sv} = 222.2 \text{ LM}^{-1}$ as compared to $kq = 165.0 \text{ LM}^{-1}$ signify that physical quenching competes with the chemical quenching.

Fig. 2

Aromatic molecules deactivate the excited uranyl ion through the π -complex formation between the aryl groups and the excited uranyl ion, since donor acceptor interaction can arise in the excited state¹². Tri-*p*-tolylphosphine has three aryl groups with methyl group substituted at *p*-position (an electron releasing group) which further enhance the deactivation of excited uranyl ion. Solvent water deactivates

the luminescent uranyl ion by hydrogen abstraction¹³. Co-ordinated water molecules deactivate via intramolecular energy transfer from uranyl ion to higher overtones of water molecules^{1,14}. The physical quenching lowers the rate and quantum yield for uranium(IV) formation.

Quantum yield and rate of uranium(IV) formation are increased with an increase in hydrogen ion concentration. Protonation of uranyl ion establishes a fast equilibrium $\text{UO}_2^{2+} + \text{H}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{UO}_2^+\text{H}$ and have higher oxidation potential and longer life time in the excited state^{15,16}.

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